

Supplementary Figure 1. Correlation between Triassic –Jurassic study sites in UK.

Lithological representations of St Audrie's Bay, Larne Northern Ireland, and Pinhay Bay sections based on field observations. St Audrie's Bay $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{org}}$ profile and duration of initial negative isotope excursion from Ruhl et al., (2010). L.Fm: Lilstock Formation, CM: Cotham Member, LM: Langport Member. Stratigraphy and ages from Ruhl et al. (2010), Bonis et al.,(2010), Hesselbo et al. (2004) and Jaraula et al. (2013) for St. Audrie's Bay. Bed number were identified follow Simms & Jeram (2007) for Larne section. For Pinhay Bay, lithological details were

obtained from Moghadam and Paul., (2000), Paul et al., (2008) and Korte et al., (2009). *C. thiergartii* marks the Triassic-Jurassic boundary (based on Jaraula et al. (2013)).

Supplementary Figure 2. Photographs of representative specimens collected from Triassic-Jurassic sections in UK. A, cutting scheme of each limestone sample. B, *Plagiostoma giganteum* from Hettangian, Lias Group, Planorbis Zone, Pinhay Bay. Dotted black lines represent shell measurements used to calculate the geometric mean for each specimen. C, *Modiolus minimus*, Hettangian, Lias Group, Planorbis Zone, Larne, NI.

Supplementary Figure 3. Stratigraphic and ecological patterns of body size change in Triassic-Jurassic bivalves. A, Average values (\pm Standard error) of body size estimated by pooling all the modes of life in each stratigraphic unit. WF: Westbury Formation, CM: Cotham Member, LM: Langport Member, PPZ: Pre-Planorbis Zone, PZ: Planorbis Zone, LZ: Liasicus Zone, AZ: Angulata Zone. B, Median body size each tier level, each boxplot represents the 5% and 95% of confidence interval and the black line (—) represents the mean body size. IN: Infaunal bivalves, SI: Semi-infaunal bivalves and SU: Surficial bivalves.

Supplementary Figure 4. Relative influence of the lithology in body size of Triassic-Jurassic

bivalves. Relative influence of the lithology in body size of Triassic-Jurassic bivalves. A, BSD of bivalves plotted for two lithologies (Limestone [—], Mudstone [---]). Each line represents the kernel density fitted to the data. B, Probability density distribution as a function of the bivalve body sizes sampled from two lithologies C, Variance of body size in bivalves estimated for each stratigraphic unit and lithology. WF: Westbury Formation, CM: Cotham Member, LM: Langport Member, PPZ: Pre-Planorbis Zone, PZ: Planorbis Zone, LZ: Liasicus Zone, AZ: Angulata Zone. D, Correlation between body-size variance from samples taken from limestone and mudstone. The correlation is high, although no significant ($p > 0.05$) due the low sample size, however this demonstrates the existence of a unique body size pattern regardless the lithology.